

NEW EQUIPMENT USED IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF DISTANCE EDUCATION**Isazade N.***Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University, teacher,
Azerbaijan***Abstract**

According to experts, distance education tools greatly simplify the educational process, make it dynamic, flexible and attractive. Advanced world experience proves the possibility of achieving successful results in education using distance education.

Unlike traditional classes, classes conducted through distance education are very attractive and interesting for both students and teachers. The use of a computer or an interactive board in the teaching process ensures the visibility of the main principles of the lesson. By gently touching the sensitive surface of the electronic board with a special pen or finger, all operations possible on the computer can be performed on it in interactive mode. A "smart" board is also a microscope, scanner, digital camera, video camera, etc. connected to a computer. can also receive images from the devices through the projector. At this time, it is possible to watch the explanation and video footage of any pedagogical facts, events and situations, the working principles of individual devices, devices, and technical means on the screen. This means that by integrating theoretical-methodological issues, practical skills and habits, it will be possible to significantly revive teaching, to approach work creatively, to think, to be proactive, to understand the teaching material more deeply. When using electronic presentations in the teaching of pedagogically oriented subjects, information is described more clearly, colorfully and dynamically. At this time, the teacher usually acts as a guide and can observe and stimulate the students' activity and freedom. In the process of giving presentations, students are at the center of the action, and they can better understand the problem situation based on their individual skills and interests. This allows the teacher to assimilate more theoretical information to the students in a short period of time (2).

Keywords: information, education, electronic, students, distance, higher school.

Implementation of the modern education model using distance education puts new demands on higher school teachers. On the other hand, high school teachers have a great responsibility for training staff according to the needs of the society.

Today, higher education teachers must use distance education to achieve high results in education. Therefore, each higher school teacher should synthesize new methodical approaches, psychological-pedagogical views and distance education knowledge along with basic knowledge in his activity.

"The experience of countries that have made significant progress in the development of education shows that modern, active-interactive training methods based on information and communication technologies, which develop creative thinking and take into account the individual characteristics of the student, give higher results. For that purpose, continuously creating progressive teaching methods and increasing the competence of teachers occupy an important place in the field of education" (4).

It is no coincidence that as one of the eight development goals of the Third Millennium adopted by all the member states of the UN, it was accepted in the direction of the development of global partnership that the opportunity to use distance education should be created.

The history of using distance education in higher education institutions of our country is very young. Nevertheless, certain measures and steps are taken in this area.

Researches show that if the teacher was the leading source of information because the 20th century educational process was built on the basis of traditional

education, the situation was different in the 21st century. Currently, the teacher acts as a mediator between information sources and students. He should teach the student effective methods of working with various sources of information, ways of obtaining information. This requires improving the content and technology of education. Therefore, higher school teachers should build a work system in accordance with the requirements of the information and innovation society (3).

The quality of pedagogical training directly depends on the knowledge, skills and activities of the teacher. One of the priority directions is the training of teaching staff on distance education within the framework of the state program. The teaching staff of the higher education system undergoes trainings for the effective use of information and communication technologies in the teaching process. Using the possibilities of distance education, they gain initial experience in conducting effective classes, psychological preparation, in short, innovative knowledge and learn how to apply them in the teaching process. According to experts, the use of distance education enriches the educational process with its visuality, gives students opportunities to conduct research, benefit from numerous information bases, choose what is necessary and use what is appropriate, and also encourages practical application of knowledge and skills.

Search It is clear from the results that in the pedagogical research conducted in the republic, the study of ways and means of purposeful use of distance education by higher school teachers was not set as a special research goal. At the same time, studies were conducted on various aspects of higher school teachers' effective use of distance education, scientific conferences were held, and current issues were discussed (4).

The introduction of distance learning technologies into the educational process makes the educational process technological and result-oriented. Yes, there are difficulties and mistakes on this path, from which it will not be possible to get rid of them in the future. But the main success is students' striving for independence, creativity, eyes shining with the desire to acquire new knowledge. The computer allows you to make the lessons different from each other. The desire to constantly innovate creates an interest in training.

A modern higher school teacher uses various modern information technology tools in his professional pedagogical activity. Today, interactive whiteboards are mostly used in educational institutions (3).

- Interactive board - is a sensitive screen (touch screen). It is connected to a computer, and displays images on the screen with the help of a projector. To start working on the computer, it is enough to touch the surface of the board. Special software allows working with objects and texts, audio and video materials. It allows the use of Internet resources, the copying of open documents and the storage of information. Interactive whiteboards open unique opportunities for work and creativity of teachers and students. This tool, which greatly helps in the organization of the training process, also helps in conducting theoretical and practical exercises. From the outside, this device does not differ from an ordinary board. But it is impossible not to feel the difference from the first acquaintance with him. Through this teaching, the work and its wide range of possibilities increases the students' interest in the subject, makes the lesson more interesting with the help of the computer, increases visibility and dynamism in the process of giving and receiving the material in the lesson, and the effectiveness of the feedback makes it immediately clear whether the material has been mastered or not.

Interactive whiteboard has a wide range of possibilities. Using this educational tool increases the effectiveness of the learning process. This self-developer is used in visual resources, in the teaching of various subjects, in teaching materials, in carrying out experiments and experiments, in providing the opportunity for modeling, and allows the use of tests to quickly determine the results on the board.

Using an interactive whiteboard really helps with training. For the teacher, the interactive whiteboard is the best tool to increase interest in the lesson and facilitate learning. The interactive whiteboard eliminates the formality of giving the material in the form of a presentation through a computer and reduces the time spent on summarizing the material (4).

Although the training conducted using the interactive whiteboard differs from the traditional methods of passing, at the same time, there is a similarity in the success of each lesson. It is possible to use the interactive board both during the entire course of the lesson and at its separate stages. The structure of lessons built using an interactive whiteboard can be different. Depending on the subject and the type of topic, teachers use different possibilities of the interactive whiteboard. Some teachers focus students' attention on the lesson by

making certain changes on the board with texts, media objects, connecting fields.

A lesson conducted with interactive devices in theoretical exercises can make any lesson dynamic, which ultimately keeps the attention of students awake throughout the lesson. Students find a lesson taught with an interactive whiteboard more interesting than a lesson taught with a regular whiteboard or by handing out written material. They admit that lessons with an interactive board are more interesting.

Higher school teachers use interactive whiteboard more in their professional activities. Especially when explaining a new lesson, attracting students' attention to the explanation of difficult materials, as well as evaluating students' knowledge on some thematic topics, performing free work, etc.

The use of an interactive board in theoretical exercises enables the activity of all students, even those who read poorly. The ability to save all the work and corrections made by students on the board for future use is also an advantage of the interactive whiteboard. It is possible to save the writings by placing them on the side of the board, which allows the teacher to refer to them at the right time.

Using remote technologies, the main goal of teachers is to develop thinking and form creative thinking.

In addition, by using remote technologies, teachers can use various teaching and demonstration programs, models and games. For this, teachers use different methods and principles also does. Teachers can use the following distance development methods and principles:

- analysis method;
- comparison method;
- generalization method;
- classification method;
- method of correcting ideas;
- internal plan of activity, etc.

Distance technologies of the higher school teacher can use the following directions of work: 1. Use of Internet resources. 2. Use of ready educational materials. 3. Preparing a presentation for the lesson. 4. Self-authored software for study and use. 5. Involve students in project work, research, preparation of presentations in the auditorium and non-auditory events, etc. (1).

In modern times, the computer provides a full opportunity for the creation of a new model of training by entering educational institutions as an individual trainer. As a result of the penetration of new technological tools that process sound, copy and information into the educational system, the creation of a modern informational educational space becomes a necessity. Because "...the information on a page stored in a computer is only eighty-thousandth of the information used to voice that page. The same can be said about television and video. A screen has an average of 300,000 dots. Each of these points represents a piece of information, and it changes on average 50 times per second. This means 15 million data per second. The amount of information obtained by watching a copy in one minute reaches one billion. For this reason, getting information from a book in the usual way or just using a blackboard

to convey information in writing is quite inadequate for video and audio (audio-visual) teaching. The speed of human information processing is so high that when learning something by reading from a book or looking at a blackboard, the brain is not fully engaged and attention can be easily distracted. As a result of the superiority of speed and sound over written information, a trend towards speed and sound interactive systems has been observed in the computer-aided teaching process over the last 15 years" (4).

Higher school teachers are trying to use the possibilities of multimedia in lessons. Multimedia is the joint integration and use of multimedia communication devices. "Multimedia is a phenomenon that can change the teaching and communication forms of today and the future and determine the role of the computer in the individual and social life of a person. It is not just simple technology, nor software, nor the skill of the user. It is an instructional technology that emerges through the use of the triad of technology, appropriate software, and a productive, skilled user" (6).

Research shows that using multimedia is another way to apply vision and hearing, the oldest learning method of mankind, in the educational process. Observations show that now students do not like to study only through books. Therefore, teachers have to turn to multimedia tools that incorporate elements such as sight, hearing, reading, and interesting images, which are all ways of learning and acquiring information. At this time, of course, teachers should have the skills to use multimedia technologies. In such a case, the teacher can be perceived by the students as an expert who can directly intervene, teach, learn, use and change events, not just comment and watch (5).

In modern educational institutions, the main content component involves informatization as a process of actively using information and communication technologies and creating normal conditions for this. The use of distance education in the work of educational institutions ensures the improvement of the educational results of most students, the compliance with the new requirements of modern social life and the labor market.

Inclusion in the training process in the management of distance education is directly related to the provision of information technologies of the educational institution. The following can be attributed to information technology in an educational institution:

- a computer room equipped with the necessary software materials, internet access, and personal computer equipment connected to the local network;
- training rooms with only one personal computer, multimedia projector and interactive board;
- the workplace of the educational institution administrative staff, which is provided with the necessary software material and has access to the Internet;
- a media library that provides access to various information resources.

Today, there is a great deal of distance technology equipment that a teacher can use. The following can be used during the preparation and conduct of the lesson:

- office technologies (MS Word, MS Excel, Power Point, etc.) that create opportunities and conditions for organizing students' creative and research activities and delivering the content of the taught subject;
- internet etc educational resources of Abeka;
- electronic educational resources that create conditions for the development of students' creative thinking and expand the possibilities of educational tools.

Distance learning resources are learning materials delivered through electronic devices. Relatively modern and effective electronic educational resources for education are available with the help of computers.

Distance education resources can be classified as follows:

1. The first level - textographic electronic educational resources that differ from a regular book in the display of text and images, that is, the material is displayed not on paper, but on the computer screen;
2. Second level - textographic electronic educational resources with the possibility to follow the text;
3. The third level - electronic educational resources consisting entirely of visual and audio fragments. The formal difference of this level from the book is that neither film, nor animation, nor sound can be published;
4. The fourth level - multimedia electronic resources with the ability to provide text, graphics, images, video, animation and sounds at the same time;
5. The fifth level - a new generation of electronic educational resources, which includes open educational modular multimedia systems. These include active author network products posted on websites and open to everyone.

Currently, several options are available for teachers to increase their computer literacy: refresher courses outside the educational institution, organization of courses within the institution itself, through mutual education and self-education. A modern high school teacher should have the ability to use information technology, such as computer technology.

References

1. Teacher training policy and problems. Proceedings of the 5th International conference. Baku: 2015, 563 p.
2. Modern problems of teacher training: technology, education and development. Proceedings of the III International Scientific Conference. / Azerbaijan Institute of Teachers. Baku: May 22-24, 2014, 508 p.
3. Nazarov A., Mammadov R. Pedagogical mastery. Baku: Teacher, 2008, 843 p.
4. Pashayev A., Rustamov F. Pedagogy, Baku: Nurlan, 2010, 464 p.
5. Rustamov F., Dadashova T. Higher school pedagogy. Baku: Nurlan, 2007, 568p.